

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

How Finnish farmers perceive the soil quality on their farms and which indicators they use

Farmers perceptions of soil quality are of high importance in the development of more sustainable farming practices. The farmer survey implemented in SoildiverAgro identified relevant agri-environmental problems in the present production as well as the most effective farming practices to face these problems. The survey data was collected from six different regions of Europe. In Finland 357 farmers provided survey answers. Of them 71% were conventional farmers and 29% organic. The survey assessed the indicators utilized by farmers to evaluate soil quality. Among all the indicators, those most commonly employed included soil structure (76% of farmers used), pH

levels (76%), and water retention capacity (61%). In Finland, also water absorption into the ground emerged as a crucial indicator (59%). Of farmers 42% followed the number of earth worms. Less used indicators were soil color or erosion. Farmers were asked about how they perceived the current average soil quality on their farms using the indicators they employed for evaluation. Soil quality was generally regarded as rather good, as 49% of respondents selecting this option, while 44% evaluated it as neither good nor bad. Of farmers 3% considered the soil quality as very good and 0% as very bad.

1. Farmers use many indicators to evaluate the soil quality

KEYWORDS

Soil quality, indicators, perceptions

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